

Dam construction, company towns and planned urban development: the example of Salto del Esla, Spain

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Abstract

Company towns are integral to the urban and territorial changes wrought by the Industrial Revolution, especially in remote, resource-rich areas. Among these, villages constructed alongside dams stand out due to their profound territorial impact. This study focuses on one such unique settlement near the Ricobayo dam in Zamora, Spain, exploring its construction and environmental integration. At its inception, Ricobayo was Europe's largest dam, its creation marked by notable feats like relocating a church, and pioneering hydraulic engineering and bridge construction, including a record-breaking design by Torroja. The adjacent company town set a precedent for creating liveable spaces for workers in isolated locales, influencing later developments. Research included on-site investigations, archival work at Iberdrola's Historical Archive, and review of historical texts, underscoring the cultural and landscape significance of 20th-century dam settlements and the distinctive features of Ricobayo's surroundings.

Keywords: planned cities, worker's town, 20th century, hydraulic works, Spain

Los poblados obreros son fundamentales para entender los cambios urbanos y territoriales provocados por la Revolución Industrial, especialmente aquellos situados en áreas remotas pero ricas en recursos. Entre ellas, destacan los poblados construidos junto a las presas debido a su profundo impacto territorial. Este estudio se centra en un asentamiento único cerca de la presa de Ricobayo en Zamora, España, y analiza tanto su construcción como su situación actual. En su momento, Ricobayo fue la presa más grande de Europa, y su construcción fue significativa debido a hechos notables como la necesidad de reubicar una iglesia, la complejidad de la obra

hidráulica o la importancia de los nuevos puentes que fueron construidos para salvar el embalse, incluyendo el célebre viaducto Martín Gil de Eduardo Torroja. El poblado sentó un precedente para crear espacios habitables para los trabajadores en localidades aisladas, e influyó en ejemplos posteriores. La investigación incluye visitas de campo, trabajo de archivo en el Archivo Histórico de Iberdrola y revisión de textos históricos, y subraya la importancia cultural y paisajística de los poblados vinculados a las presas del siglo XX y las características distintivas del ejemplo de Ricobayo.

Keywords: ciudades planificadas, poblado industrial, siglo XX, obras hidráulicas, España.

Introduction

The settlements built throughout the 20th century to serve dam workers constitute one of the urban milestones of planned urbanism in Spain.¹ These settlements were erected in the vicinity of large dams, often located in depopulated areas, to house the workers who would participate in the construction of these works and later in their exploitation. Despite their small size, it was necessary for them to provide the services their inhabitants needed to carry out their daily lives. Therefore, they usually included shops, educational and religious facilities, civil guard barracks, small hospitals, or even theatres. In the surroundings of each dam, there could be several settlements, either temporary or permanent, promoted by the construction contract or by the company or administration promoting them.²

New towns developed for dam workers have origins in workers' settlements, often called 'company towns', established during the Industrial Revolution. These emerged as a solution to the worsening conditions of urban working-class areas in the 18th and 19th centuries. Notable examples include New Lanark in Scotland, started by David Dale and Robert Owen in 1786 for 2,500 residents, Tremadog in Wales in 1811 by William Madocks, Lowell in the U.S. around 1820 by the Merrimack Manufacturing Company and, later, Saltaire in Yorkshire, built by Titus Salt from 1851.³ In the late 19th century, other planned towns arose, such as the one led by railway tycoon George Pullman built near Chicago, Illinois in 1884, designed for 4,000 employees with amenities like theatres and parks.⁴ Another is Derry Church, later renamed Hershey in Pennsylvania, founded by chocolatier Milton Hershey in 1903.⁵ The 20th century saw the emergence of towns like Cokedale in Colorado, built in 1907 by ASARCO for lead and zinc production, which was meticulously planned, and Jamshedpur in India, built around a steel plant.⁶ Throughout the 20th century, larger regional projects were launched to accommodate vast populations across different areas. For example, several towns in the Agro Pontino region of Italy were founded in the 1930s.⁷ Furthermore, in Spain's Asturias Region, the mining company Ensidesa built housing complexes like Llaranes in 1954.⁸ In Morocco, a significant

post-war rural development programme was initiated by the United Nations after independence.⁹ Another significant effort was the growth in California's Los Angeles area to support the burgeoning aeronautics sector in the early 1960s.¹⁰ Currently, some of these housing groups are understood as fundamental elements of industrial landscapes, such as the case of the Slate Landscape of Northwest Wales or the Derwent Valley linked to the mechanised cotton spinning in Derbyshire.¹¹

In most of these settlements, there was a need to provide workers and their families with a place to live. There was also an intention to project urbanisation that could follow the lines of garden cities, with scattered buildings or traditional villages with continuous street frontages and plazas. The distinguishing feature of these settlements is always the morphological, structural, and landscape relationship with the activity they serve. Thus, in the case of dam villages, the relationship between the dam, water sheet, management house, and residential complex is crucial. Over time, permanent settlements end up forming a landscape together with the rest of the elements associated with the dam.

This article focuses on the permanent settlement built to serve one of Spain's most unique dams, Ricobayo or Esla (Figure 1), which is part of the complex called the 'Duero hydro-electric falls'. It consists of a 99m-high dam that backs up a reservoir of 1,145 million m³, and a power plant at the foot of the dam with an installed capacity of 133 MW, to which another 158 MW would be added decades later. The works were planned in 1928 and began in June 1929; on 4 January 1935, the supply of electricity began, with the Bilbao area as its first recipient. With the Ricobayo dam, an energy source was created that was five times the national electricity consumption of that time.¹² The magnitude of the works prompted a visit from King Alfonso XIII on 20 October 1930, and his famous words were: 'These works will continue above all

current concerns because uniting everyone, monarchists and republicans, is the idea of the homeland'.¹³

The dam (Figure 2) is one of the major engineering works built in Spain in the 20th century, creating the largest reservoir in Europe at its completion, and stands out for various reasons. Firstly, it was the first project to be completed within a large set developed over the years in the western part of the Duero River basin by the company 'Saltos del Duero'.¹⁴ Additionally, the dam's construction led to the relocation, stone by stone, of the significant Visigoth temple of San Pedro de la Nave, declared a National Monument in 1912, because it was situated in the flood zone of the new reservoir.¹⁵ This relocation was already included in the concession contract and represented a pioneering intervention in Western European heritage carried out by architect Alejandro Ferrant (Figure 2).¹⁶

Another unique event associated with the work was the erosion near the dam caused by the water discharge from the initially-designed spillway: in 1934, when the construction was coming to an end (the dam had been closed in the summer of 1933, and all floodwater was already exiting through the spillway), a flow of over 5,000 m³/s subjected the spillway to an immense abrasive action. Despite the apparent solidity of the rocky substrate, the sudden water infiltration through the fissures created a wedge effect that caused the granitic boulders to pop out and slide on the joint clay. On 22 and 23 March, 1934, the spillway canal suffered a significant regressive collapse, and a large crater emerged where the water fell. This required the construction of a hydraulic laboratory to study the issue using scale models, becoming one of the pioneering cases in this field.¹⁷ The problem was solved by a team that included engineer Theodor Rebock from the University of Karlsruhe and Swiss consultant Arnold Kaesch.¹⁸ A total lining solution was defined for the area eroded by the floods using concrete, a new spillway

tunnel was constructed, and a dam was built to regulate the water level at the exit of the power plant.

Lastly, the new reservoir became a significant physical barrier, necessitating the construction of large structures to serve the railway and roads. Notable among them is the Martín Gil Bridge, designed by the outstanding engineer Eduardo Torroja in 1939, a pioneering work for its construction method and, at the time, the largest arch span in the world (Figure 2).¹⁹ There was also the noteworthy Manzanal bridge designed by Díaz Burgos in 1942.²⁰ It is worth noting that various structures were submerged by the reservoir, such as the stone bridge of La Estrella from 1869. (Some sources, perhaps with little consistency, indicate that it could have been designed by Práxedes Mateo Sagasta, who later became the Prime Minister of Spain seven times).²¹

In this context, the village is a significant landmark associated with the Esla dam, and it should be understood as a core element for the development of the works. It has distinctive qualities that make it a prominent example among the Spanish dam villages, especially given the pioneering nature of everything that surrounded the dam's construction. It has been pointed out that:

It was the largest project carried out in Spain at that time, providing employment to thousands of workers (machinists, electricians, mechanics, masons, carpenters, guards, and drillers), foremen and technicians, even establishing a model village near the waterfall in Muelas del Pan, equipped with a school, co-op, church, dispensary, and canteen.²²

For this research, the surroundings of the village and the dam have been visited on several occasions. Historical documents and photographs related to the village have also been examined, both in the Historical Archive of Iberdrola (AHI) and in historical periodicals.

Previous publications related to the villages and other examples of planned urbanism linked to industrial activities in rural areas have also been consulted.

First Village Project

The company promoting the Ricobayo dam, the *Sociedad Hispano-Portuguesa de Transportes Eléctricos* (Hispano-Portuguese Society of Electric Transport), known as *Saltos del Duero*, was established in 1927 with the primary objective of harnessing the hydroelectric potential of the Duero River. This was during a time in Europe when hydroelectric power generation was gaining significance. In its early years, the company began identifying and studying the best locations along the Duero River for the construction of dams and hydroelectric plants. These initial studies led to several projects that would shape the company's future, notably the Ricobayo, Villalcampo, Saucelle, and Aldeadávila dams. It is essential to mention that the Duero River forms part of the border between Spain and Portugal. Therefore, from its inception, Saltos del Duero had to work collaboratively with Portuguese authorities. This cooperation resulted in bilateral agreements between both countries and a coordinated approach to the river's hydroelectric projects. José Orbegozo y Gorostegui was the company's first general director, succeeded by Ricardo Rubio Sacristán in 1935.²³

Regarding the Ricobayo dam, the construction site was located far from any significant population. Additionally, the terrain was rugged, making road communications with the surrounding villages challenging. The provincial capital, Zamora, had all the basic services but was 25 km away from the works. Therefore, from the outset, it was decided to set up a camp to serve the construction workers around 1928-9. The project was designed by the aforementioned civil engineer José Orbegozo Gorostegui, who was also responsible for the dam project and one of the main promoters of hydraulic works in Spain at that time.²⁴ The entire construction, both the camp and the dam, was carried out by the companies Sociedad General de Obras y Construcciones (Obrascón, now OHL), and Puertos y Pantanos S.A.²⁵

The settlement was located on the left bank of the river, adjacent to the construction area, and housed about 2,000 people.²⁶ In several articles published in the *Revista de Obras Públicas* journal, Orbezo himself described the auxiliary facilities provided for the work, and in one of them, he detailed the proposed camp, the building facilities, and the supply, sanitation, and electricity networks, noting that ‘the accommodation of the worker, administrative, and technical staff requires the construction of a camp or village, in which water and electricity are the most essential elements’.²⁷

The buildings constructed were of two types: temporary and permanent (Figures 3, 4, 5). The temporary ones were built with wood on masonry foundations, had a rectangular prism shape, and were removable (Figure 4). This group consisted of ten pavilions, each with ten individual homes for families; four pavilions with eight sections, each arranged for nine workers hosted by a couple; and a shared dormitory for workers, along with a dining room that could accommodate 80 people. The church, the market, schools, laundry, gym, showers, barbershop, and a performance hall were also temporary.

On the other hand, the permanent buildings were designed to be used later by the staff in charge of exploiting the dam and were built with solid materials. The complex included the management building (Figure 6), the administration house (whose ground floor was designated for an office and material testing laboratory, while the upper floor housed accommodations for administrative and technical staff), the lodging house (with housing on its upper floor for supervisors and similar staff), the civil guard barracks, and a commissary.

A significant fact is that for the construction of the camp, and in order to prevent possible outbreaks of epidemics and diseases, they sought the advice of Dr. José Román Manzanete, a

renowned bacteriologist associated with the Rockefeller Foundation.²⁸ He defined the parameters of the water supply and sanitation networks, as well as water treatment and waste management.²⁹ The water was sourced from the Esla River, upstream of the dam construction, and was transferred to a raised tank in the highest elevation of the surroundings, where a series of treatments took place. The anticipated allocation was about 220l per inhabitant per day, a quantity greater than even that required by the 1924 law for cities of more than 15,000 inhabitants in Spain, which amounted to 200l per inhabitant per day.³⁰ This was also greater than other settlements built in the 1950s and 1960s, where they planned for 100l per inhabitant per day.³¹

Projects of the 1950s

The temporary buildings of the camp were demolished after the works, although the exact date is unknown. In any case, the permanent structures were not enough to service the operational dam. Hence, in the 1950s, Iberduero, the successor company to Saltos del Duero from 1944 onwards, initiated a significant expansion. Thus, in 1954, a project was approved for a settlement for the operational staff of the dam³², which included an initial draft for 68 homes for the dam's operational staff (Figure 7). Both documents were drafted by the Bilbao architect Francisco Hurtado de Saracho.³³

In the project report, the need to build a settlement with all kinds of social and religious services was justified due to the distance from the dam to the nearest urban centres. The conceived programme included 68 homes of three types (Table 1), a garage area on the ground floor, commercial spaces, and a church of 400m². Likewise, the necessary infrastructure works were projected, which included roads, street paving, sanitation, water supply, and electricity. A subsequent additional village project for the hydroelectric power plant staff from November 1956, also drafted by Hurtado (Table 2), incorporated a school, small hospital, chicken coops, water facilities, electrical installation, and the access road to the village; the latter is formed of

straight alignments and constant-radius curves, with a slope of up to 7.6% in some sections.³⁴ However, a casino-cinema announced in the project would not be executed. The total garden area reached 7.04ha, with a total built area of 0.43ha.

The residential buildings were constructed using beams and hollow concrete blocks made of vibrated concrete. The external walls were executed with half-brick masonry, with an air gap and an interior partition wall, and the roofs were constructed of wood, covered with tiles (Figure 8). The school was designed in a building with separate single classrooms for boys and girls (54 desks each). On the other hand, the small hospital consists of a two-storey building: on the lower floor there are a consultation room, office, treatment room, X-rays, toilets, and two rooms, one for the sick and another for the injured; the upper floor is reserved for the doctor's residence. The hen houses were set apart from the village, with separate areas for chickens and pigs. Regarding the church, it is a building with a single nave and side rooms, including a sacristy, on the corners. A notable feature is the space designed outside, with a porticoed atrium that connects the facade with a detached bell tower.

Description of the Village

Although the current village is actually the sum of three projects, it appears quite harmonious. The buildings are vaguely staggered, with the facades more or less aligned with the contour lines, respecting the topography, which has a slope that descends towards the Esla. The road network consists of two streets that wind between the buildings and meet at the two access points, one upper and one lower. The pedestrian network is segregated from the roads and runs between the gardens and trees of the ensemble, connecting the houses with the school located in the lower part of the slope. The main facades face approximately west, following contour lines, and it seems they were not designed with the aim of achieving optimal lighting.

The northern area clusters the administrative and management buildings, which remain from the original camp, and the southern part houses those of a residential nature, which are more recent. In the centre is the church, surrounded by gardens with its bell tower standing out above the rooftops, rising 12m from its base (Figure 9). Meanwhile, the management building is located at one end on a platform with magnificent views of the dam, featuring a viewpoint in its gardens (Figure 6).

From a landscaping perspective, the town stands out for its harmonious adaptation to its surroundings. This charming town, primarily made up of one or two-storey buildings, blends seamlessly with the natural terrain without the need for significant earthwork. Additionally, it maintains consistency with the traditional architectural elements of the area, like washed facades adorned with stone details and red-tiled roofs. A standout feature of the ensemble is the supply tower, located on the hill in the upper area of the slope, reaching a height of 21m.

The set is reminiscent of garden cities, with a clear separation of functional areas, that knows how to play with the environment by placing the management area at the most privileged point, the buildings with the greatest surface and therefore the most volume in the lower areas and the houses in the upper areas, conveniently separated from each other, ensuring enough open space between one and the other but maintaining a certain proximity to guarantee the feeling of a set. White wooden fences also separate some gardens from others.

Analysis and conclusions

The village of Esla, like other similar examples, shows the company's intention to provide its workers with an ideal place to live their lives: the houses were spacious, they formed a harmonious set, adapted to their environment and offered enough outdoor space for the inhabitants to feel in a cozy place; this is also confirmed by the concern to provide an adequate

water supply, to guarantee food supply through their own pens, and to incorporate educational, cultural, leisure, and religious facilities into the settlement. Similarly, to design the buildings erected in the 1950s, the company relied on a prestigious architect, just as the Hidroeléctrica Española Spanish Company would when collaborating with Miguel Oriol and Fernando Urrutia in the towns of Tajo, or Electricidade De Portugal, whose settlements in the Zêzere river basin were designed by Miguel Jacobetty Rosa.³⁵ The idea of proposing a welcoming environment made sense, as Chapa Imaz points out:

Life in the towns and camps of the works generated a micro-society based on the styles of Spanish society of the time, perfectly structured to achieve collective goals. On many occasions, exhaustion occurred due to fatigue and, above all, the permanence of so many months living in a reduced space.³⁶

Another sign of the company's will to 'make society' is *Don Voltio*, a publication by Iberduero that between 1959 and 1962 sought to create a sense of a worker community, especially those scattered through the towns (Figure 10). In the first issue, the Esla town was mentioned, indicating for example that 'the only thing missing from the water tank to make it look like a windmill is wind and blades. Of course, if it also had these two things, more than one would believe they lived in La Mancha'. It was also noted that the facades of the buildings were painted in various colours (green, yellow or blue), that the church bells were electric, and that 'children keep being born. It's a good thing these things happen everywhere'.³⁷

What sets this village apart from others is its diverse origins: it is unusual that the original project by Orbegozo did not plan for enough permanent homes for the exploitation of the dam. This circumstance, not clarified in Hurtado de Saracho's project memories, might be due to the Esla being a pioneering dam in Spain, and for that reason, its planning and management were also pioneering. Likely, the experience gained would be crucial for the design of villages

surrounding subsequent dams. Another unique feature is the absence of a permanent church in the original camp, perhaps due to the era in which it was built, the 1920s, a time of diminishing religious observance, especially when compared to Francoist Spain (1936-1975), a period when the villages built to support many new dams all had churches. The village section projected by Orbegozo, built during the Franco dictatorship, did have a permanent church. It is also worth considering whether it might have been possible to use the relocated San Pedro de la Nave church for the village. After all, there was a debate at the time about keeping it near its original location or even moving it to Zamora.³⁸ It can be noted that a village built later, by the Aldeadávila dam, took advantage of an old convent to construct the entire village around it.³⁹

Another significant difference regarding subsequent villages is that when this one was built, nearly 300 colonisation villages planned by the INC (*Instituto Nacional de Colonización*, or National Institute of Colonisation) in various Spanish provinces had neither been projected nor built. Such villages would influence both the aesthetics and urban planning of dam villages in Extremadura.⁴⁰

However, the Esla village does have features that subsequent villages would follow: management buildings are more architecturally intricate than houses and serve a symbolic role, akin to the castles of feudal Europe or the 19th-century opera houses in major cities. They stand in a separate area, and their symbolic nature represents the company power within a political framework and the dominance of the engineering elite over both the workforce and the environment they aim to tame. Furthermore, the area where the director's house is located stands out, overlooking the whole site. This feature will be common in later villages, such as those in the Badajoz plan or those in the Tajo, like the unique case of Valdecañas.⁴¹

In a global framework, the Esla settlement represents a pioneering example in Spain's typological history of settlements. It is postulated that it may have served as a blueprint for subsequent settlements within both national and European contexts, something logical considering that the Esla was one of the first major European dams, the first in Spain, and held the continental record upon its completion. However, it is acknowledged that comprehensive scientific literature on this topic remains scant. Indeed, one prominent inference from our study is the evident need for further exploration and research in this domain.

When juxtaposed with the 'company cities' delineated in the introductory segment, Esla's design philosophy seems to display an advanced maturity. Its approach surpasses earlier 18th-century exemplars like New Lanark in Scotland or Guise in Belgium. This is evident in its incorporation of 'garden city' tenets, reminiscent of later settlements such as Pullman, Hersey, or Cokedale, where green spaces are integral, and every working family is provided individual housing. A distinct innovation in Esla's design is its unconventional architectural layout. Contrary to the conventional linear alignment of dwellings along roads or the ubiquitous grid-based road system, Esla's design ethos emphasises conformity to the natural topography. This not only ensures a more organic and visually harmonious integration with the landscape but also prioritises pedestrian mobility between homes, the village's communal zones, and work sites.

Furthermore, it is pertinent to note that while company towns typically associated with factories often favoured flat terrains, those related to dams confronted topographical challenges. Dams, by their nature, are situated in enclosed valleys with pronounced gradients. In this context, Esla's design shares a conceptual kinship with New Lanark, which employs elongated pavilions parallel to the river. Moreover, the spatial segregation strategy, demarcating the residential zones of workers from company executives and positioning shared amenities centrally, is a

recurring motif in the analysed company towns, and also in the subsequent colonisation towns erected in Spain during the following decades.

On the other hand, research has highlighted the constructive, morphological, and landscape values of the village, contributing landmarks to the territory like the water tank, the management building, or the bell tower, thereby characterising the area where it is located (Figure 11). But its importance goes beyond, as the planned settlement belongs to an outstanding engineering ensemble - mentioned in the introduction - spread across a vast territory, with its virtues and peculiarities shaping a water-related engineering landscape. In this context, the growing importance in Spain of cultural landscapes associated with the accumulation of public works has been pointed out, and this case could be another one, thanks to the described ensemble.⁴² It is a rural landscape that continues to evolve, incorporating elements like engineer Santiago Pérez-Fadón's COR-TEN steel bridge (Figure 11), which finds its *raison d'être* in the Esla dam.⁴³ The research also shows the need to understand the history and staggered development of what we see; thus, one might think the current village was built uniformly during the dam's construction period when we now know this is not the case. Regarding the barracks from the initial village, none have stood the test of time. The materials used in their construction might have contributed to their inability to be preserved until now. Future research is needed to uncover the nature of these settlements and the amenities they provided to their residents, possibly using additional historical photos. Lastly, we believe this study can be the starting point for future research that delves deeper into the heritage and historical values of the engineering works in the entire Ricobayo area. It can also be helpful to understand other villages built on the Duero river by the same company afterward, which probably took this Esla one as an example.

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Caption list

Figure 1: Left: Dam location in NW Iberian Peninsula, near Zamora. Right: Settlement position relative to dam, showing the power plant and spillway.

Figure 2: Left: Martín Gil Bridge and Ricobayo Dam with modified spillway. Right: Relocation of San Pedro de la Nave Church and reconstructed temple.

Figure 3: Reproduction of the workers' camp with accommodations arranged in parallel rows, separating residential and service areas (source: Revista de Obras Públicas).

Figure 4: Village view featuring both permanent and temporary buildings. (c1930s postcards, author's collection)

Figure 5: Image from Engineering and Construction magazine showing the camp built for Esla jump works, highlighting houses, administration, and commissary (source: *Ingeniería y Construcción*). Detail of barracks below.

Figure 6: Management building and dam lookout.

Figure 7: Plans of the second settlement from initial and final projects. The location of the church is perhaps the most significant change between the two. The non-shaded buildings are the survivors of the original camp (source: AHI).

Figure 8. Historical images from the Iberdrola archive. On the right, village with dam in foreground; on the left, condition of houses and road (source: AHI).

Figure 9. Blueprints of the church, and its current situation (source: AHI). It is notable that the existence of a slightly flatter area is utilised for the atrium; the tower was placed in the area with the greatest slope, perhaps to enhance the feeling of height and slenderness (source: AHI).

Figure 10: Covers from 'don Voltio' magazine featuring images of Esla village and church in the August 1959 issue, and a residential area in the June/July 1960 issue (source: AHI).

Figure 11: Top row: Views of the village, pedestrian network, and inn. Bottom row: Water reservoir tower from Muelas del Pan and Ricobayo arch.

Table 1. Features of the proposed homes.

Type	Number constructed	Total area (m ²)	Usable area (m ²)	Cost pts/m ²	Rooms	Typology
A	30	96	74	1460	Kitchen-dining room, four bedrooms, toilet and pantry	Semi-detached on two floors
B	28	87	66	1220	Kitchen-dining room, three bedrooms and toilet	Semi-detached on two floors
C	10	72	55	2029	Kitchen-dining room,	In a block, forming a square

					three bedrooms and toilet	
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Table 2. Budget summary for the two projects: the village and the additional one.

Element (First Phase)	Budget cost (millions of pesetas) (First Phase)	Element (Second Phase)	Budget cost (millions of pesetas) (Second Phase)
30 type A houses	3.081	Schools	0.45
28 type B houses	2.167	Small hospital and doctor's house	0.334
10 type C houses and garages	1.071	Chicken coops	0.304
Church	0.433	Water supply	0.913
Infrastructure	0.968	Electric power supply	1.159
Total material execution budget	7.721	Access road to the village	1.243
15% Industrial profit and general expenses	1.158	Total material execution budget	4.403
Bonuses	1.07	15% Industrial profit and general expenses	0.662
Total contracting budget	9.949	Architect's fees	0.158
Architect's fees	0.241	Technical architect's fees	0.057
Technical architect's fees	0.087	Taxes	0.08
Taxes	0.012	Land purchase cost	0.164
Land purchase cost	0.318	Total	5.452
Total	10.607		

¹ Maria Jesús Teixidó Domínguez, 'El poblado del embalse de Alcántara: un ejemplo de urbanismo en el período de la Autarquía', in *Paisajes modelados por el agua: entre el arte y la*

ingeniería, ed. María del Mar Lozano Bartolozzi and Vicente Méndez Hernán (Cáceres: Editora Regional de Extremadura, 2012), 235–245; Pedro Plasencia-Lozano, ‘Los poblados construidos por el Estado en las presas del Plan Badajoz, elementos de urbanismo planificado en el paisaje rural extremeño’, in *Paisajes culturales del agua*, ed. María del Mar Lozano Bartolozzi and Vicente Méndez Hernán (Cáceres: Universidad de Extremadura, 2017), 169–87; María del Mar Lozano Bartolozzi, ‘Poblados de nueva planta en la cuenca media Del Tajo’, *Ábaco. Revista de Cultura y Ciencias Sociales* 80–81 (2014): 62–68.

² Pedro Plasencia-Lozano and Marina Bargón, ‘An analysis of the small planned towns built for the workers of the Badajoz Plan dams in Spain’, *Planning Perspectives*, 2023.

³ Philip Cooke, ‘Silicon Valley imperialists create New Model villages as Smart Cities in their own image’, *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity* 6, no. 2 (2020): 24.

⁴ Janice L Reiff, ‘Rethinking Pullman’, *Social Science History* 24, no. 1 (2000): 7–26.

⁵ James Dennis McMahon, ‘Milton Hershey’s world’, *Pennsylvania History: a Journal of Mid-Atlantic Studies* 88, no. 4 (2021): 548–85.

⁶ Hemalata C. Dandekar, ‘Review essay: Planned one-company towns and unplanned allegiances’, *Journal of Planning History* 9, no. 1 (2010): 66–70; Amita Sinha and Jatinder Singh, ‘Jamshedpur: planning an ideal steel city in India’, *Journal of Planning History* 10, no. 4 (2011): 263–81.

⁷ Maria Martone, ‘Le trasformazioni territoriali dell’area Pontina nel XX Secolo. La riconoscibilità storica dei luoghi nella iconografia tra Ottocento e Novecento: alcuni esempi’, *Eikonocity* 1, no. 1 (2016): 133–45; Moisés Bazán de Huerta and María del Mar Lozano Bartolozzi, ‘El Agro Pontino italiano y los pueblos de Colonización en la provincia de Cáceres’, *BSAA Arte* 81 (2015): 203–29.

⁸ Natalia Tielve García, ‘Company towns: architecture and paternalism. From the Compagnie Royale Asturienne Des Mines to Cristalería Española’, *Estoa* 7, no. 12 (2018): 123–35. It

should also be highlighted that in Spain, in particular, planned urbanism related to workers has been investigated by different authors, with multidisciplinary methodological approaches and extensive documentary bases. Among others, we can highlight the works of Mercè Tatjer, José Sierra Álvarez, Carlos Sambricio, Manuel Valenzuela o Carlos Yepes Rodríguez. Mercè Tatjer, ‘La vivienda obrera en la España de los Siglos XIX y XX: de la promoción privada a la promoción pública (1853-1975)’, *Scripta Nova: Revista Electrónica de Geografía y Ciencias Sociales* 9 (2005); José Sierra Álvarez, ‘Política de vivienda y disciplinas industriales paternalistas en Asturias’, *Ería* 0, no. 8 (1985): 61–71; Carlos Sambricio, *Un siglo de vivienda social: 1903-2003* (Madrid: Nerea, 2003); Manuel Valenzuela Rubio, ‘Las sociedades constructoras benéficas, una respuesta paternalista al problema de la vivienda obrera: su incidencia en la configuración de la periferia madrileña (1875-1921)’, in *Anales Del Instituto de Estudios Madrileños* (Madrid: Instituto de Estudios Madrileños, 1983), 63–96; Carlos Andrés Yepes Rodríguez, *La revista ‘Hogar y arquitectura’ de 1955 a 1977: Modelando la vivienda social* (Barcelona: Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, 2020).

⁹ Michele Tenzon and Axel Fisher, ‘Foreign aid for rural development: village design and planning in Post-Independence Morocco’, *Planning Perspectives* 37, no. 5 (2022): 949–71.

¹⁰ Layne Karafantis and Stuart W. Leslie, ‘“Suburban warriors”: The Blue-Collar and Blue-Sky communities of Southern California’s aerospace industry’, *Journal of Planning History* 18, no. 1 (2019): 3–26.

¹¹ Gwyn, David. ‘“The Slate Landscape of Northwest Wales’ — A New Industrial World Heritage Site’, *Industrial Archaeology Review* 45, no. 1 (2023): 19–31; Lilley, Suzanne. ‘Stitching Together the Fabric of Industrial Houses: Investigating the Origins and Development of Cotton Workers’ Accommodation in the Derwent Valley, Derbyshire’, *Industrial Archaeology Review* 39, no. 2 (2017): 117–28.

¹² Jaime De la Fuente, José María Sánchez-Moreno, Raquel López and Manuel Villén. *De Obrascón a OHL. Crónica de un centenario. 1911-2011* (Madrid: OHL, 2011).

¹³ Yolanda Diego Martín, ‘Archivo Histórico de Iberdrola. Fuentes documentales para la investigación histórica de la industria eléctrica en Zamora’, in *Nec Otium XIX XX XXI*, ed. José Luis Hernando Garrido (Zamora: Museo Etnográfico de Castilla y León, 2007), 180–95.

¹⁴ Gregorio Núñez, *La construcción de los Saltos Del Duero, 1930–1970. Historia de una epopeya colectiva* (Pamplona: Ediciones de la Universidad de Navarra, 1999).

¹⁵ Luis Caballero Zoreda and Fernando Arce, ‘La iglesia de San Pedro de la Nave (Zamora). Arqueología y arquitectura’, *Archivo Español de Arqueología* 70, no. 175–176 (1997): 221–74.

¹⁶ Vicente Machimbarrena Goyorza, ‘Saltos Del Duero: aprovechamiento de aguas del río Esla’, *Revista de Obras Públicas* 2544 (1930): 93–97; María Pilar García Cuetos, ‘Alejandro Ferrant y Manuel Gómez-Moreno: aplicación del método científico del CEH a la restauración monumental’, *Loggia, Arquitectura & Restauración* 21 (2008): 8.

¹⁷ Bill Addis, ‘The historical use of physical model testing in free-surface hydraulic engineering’, in *Physical Models*, (London: Wiley, 2020), 663–710.

¹⁸ Pascual Riesco, ‘El embalse de Ricobayo y la visita en 1934 de Theodor Rehbock’, in *Congreso Conmemorativo 1929 - 2009. 80 Años de Historia Del Salto Del Esla (Zamora)*, (Zamora: 2009); Eduard Callís Freixas, ‘Aprendiendo de las presas: la mirada de la arquitectura a la obra hidráulica’, in *Congreso Internacional Historia de la Arquitectura Moderna Española, ‘Los Edificios de la Industria: Icono y Espacio de Progreso Para la Arquitectura en el Arranque de la Modernidad* (Pamplona: Universidad de Navarra, 2021), 1–16.

¹⁹ Eduardo Torroja, ‘El gran arco del viaducto Francisco Martín Gil’, *Informes de la Construcción* 137, no. 14 (1962): 157–70; Daniel Crespo, David Fernández-Ordóñez and Bernardo Revuelta, ‘Civil engineering heritage: country profile 1 – Spain’, *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Engineering History and Heritage* 169, no. 1 (2016): 42–45.

²⁰ Antonio Díaz Burgos, ‘Puente para camino vecinal sobre el embalse del Esla en Manzanal Del Barco (Zamora)’, *Revista de Obras Públicas* 2724 (1942): 182–84.

²¹ ‘Puente de Piedra de la Estrella’, *Revista de Obras Públicas* 17 (1869), 159–60; Fernando Sáenz Ridruejo, ‘Práxedes Mateo Sagasta, Ingeniero de Caminos’, *Berceo* 139 (2000), 67–92.

²² Carlos Piñel, *Sueños de plata. El tiempo y los ritos. Fotografía y antropología en Castilla y León* (Zamora: Editorial de Ureña, 2012); Yolanda Diego Martín, ‘Archivo Histórico de Iberdrola. Fuentes documentales para la investigación histórica de la industria eléctrica en Zamora’, in *Nec Otium XIX XX XXI*, ed. José Luis Hernando Garrido (Zamora: Museo Etnográfico de Castilla y León, 2007), 180–95.

²³ Pascual Riesco, ‘El Embalse de Ricobayo y la visita En 1934 de Theodor Rehbock’, in *Congreso Conmemorativo 1929 - 2009. 80 Años de Historia Del Salto Del Esla (Zamora)*, (Zamora: 2009).

²⁴ Fernando Arroyo Ilera, ‘Territorio, tecnología y capital : la regulación hidroeléctrica de los ríos españoles (1900-1970)’, *Treballs de la Societat Catalana de Geografia* 0, no. 63 (2008): 39–70.

²⁵ Pablo Díaz Morlán, ‘Los Saltos Del Duero (1918-1944)’, in *Un Siglo de Luz. Historia Empresarial de Iberdrola* (Bilbao: Fundación Iberdrola, 2006), 279–325.

²⁶ ‘Los Saltos Del Duero. El Salto Del Esla’, *Ingeniería y Construcción* 83 (1929): 596.

²⁷ José Orbegozo Gorostegui, ‘Saltos Del Duero: los grandes medios auxiliares de construcción del aprovechamiento de Aguas Del Río Esla’, *Revista de Obras Públicas* 2558 (1930): 437–41.

²⁸ Mariano Monge Juárez, ‘La II República contra las fiebres tifoideas: vertebración del territorio y agua potable. Aproximación histórica a las políticas legislativas y preventivas, 1931-1939’, *Ebre 38: Revista Internacional de la Guerra Civil, 1936-1939* 11, no. 11 (2021): 111–23.

²⁹ José Román Manzanete, ‘Saltos del Duero: aprovechamiento de aguas del río Esla’, *Revista de Obras Públicas* 2547 (1930): 167–74.

³⁰ Juan Manuel Matés, ‘Water supply regulation in Spain: 19th and 20th Centuries’, *Revista de Historia Industrial* 25, no. 61 (2016): 15–47.

³¹ Pedro Plasencia-Lozano, ‘Los poblados de las presas, urbanismo para obreros. Análisis comparativo de tres conjuntos singulares’, in *Paisajes culturales entre el Tajo y el Guadiana*, ed. María del Mar Lozano Bartolozzi and Vicente Méndez Hernán (Cáceres: Universidad de Extremadura, 2018), 195–214.

³² Iberdrola Historical Archive AHI ST-416-17

³³ Iberdrola Historical Archive AHI ST-356-32

³⁴ Iberdrola Historical Archive AHI ST-421-14

³⁵ Fernando Pérez Rodríguez-Urrutia, ‘El poblado de Valdecañas. Modelo de integración en un paisaje fluvial o hidrocolonización’, in *Paisajes modelados por el agua: entre el arte y la ingeniería*, ed. María del Mar Lozano Bartolozzi and Vicente Méndez Hernán (Cáceres: Universidad de Extremadura, 2012), 167–86; Pedro Plasencia-Lozano, ‘Los poblados de las presas, urbanismo para obreros. Análisis comparativo de tres conjuntos singulares’.

³⁶ Álvaro Chapa Imaz, ‘Los Saltos del Duero. Reflexión sobre una investigación histórica’, in *Nec Otium XIX XX XXI*, ed. José Luis Hernando Garrido (Zamora: Museo Etnográfico de Castilla y León, 2007), 120–133.

³⁷ ‘Chispazos del Esla’, *Don Voltio* 1 (1959): 7.

³⁸ María Pilar García Cuetos, ‘Las primeras experiencias de desmonte y traslado de monumentos en Francia y España’, *Gremium* 6, no. 11 (2019): 22–35.

³⁹ Pedro Martínez Artola, ‘Salto de Aldeadávila, España’, *Informes de la Construcción* 19, no. 180 (1966): 37–52.

⁴⁰ Pedro Plasencia-Lozano, ‘Los poblados de las presas, urbanismo para obreros. Análisis comparativo de tres conjuntos singulares’.

⁴¹ María del Mar Lozano Bartolozzi, ‘Poblados de nueva planta en la cuenca media del Tajo’.

⁴² Rita Ruiz, Linarejos Cruz, Francisco Javier Rodríguez and José María Coronado, ‘Civil engineering heritage in Spain: public protection strategies’, *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Engineering History and Heritage* 169, no. 2 (2016): 84–94.

⁴³ Santiago Pérez-Fadón Martínez and José Emilio Herrero Beneit, ‘Proyecto y construcción del Arco de Ricobayo’, *Hormigón y Acero* 50, no. 212 (1999).